

**ELIXIR IT All Hands Meeting 2023
and
ELIXIR-IT - Rare Diseases Community Workshop**

ISS and ELIXIR a joint effort for the RD Community

Claudio Carta

Istituto Superiore di Sanita'
Local Technical Coordinator ELIXIR IT
Member of the ISC-IRDIRC

CNR, 27-29 November 2023

Since 2014, ISS and ELIXIR, a Joint effort for the RD Community

October 2017 [View this email in your browser](#)

ELIXIR weekly brief

Updates from Use Cases

Read the report from the **International Summer School on Rare Disease and Orphan Drug Registries and "Bring Your Own Data" workshop** organised by the ELIXIR Rare Disease Use Case in Rome, Italy on 18-22 September.

ESHG 2015 Glasgow
European Society of Human Genetics
Glasgow, Scotland, UK, June 2015

Linked data approach: some results and considerations from the first RD-Connect Bring Your Own Data meeting in Rome

10th International SWAT4HCLS Conference

Semantic Web Applications and Tools for Health Care and Life Sciences

December 4-7, 2017
Rome, Italy

ELIXIR All Hands 2016

ELIXIR Rare Disease Use Case & RD-CONNECT

Linked Registries Hackathon

RD-Connect Linked Data & Ontologies Task Force and friends
ISS, Rome, November 26-27 th **2014**

9th International SWAT4LS Conference

Semantic Web Applications and Tools for the Life Sciences

December 5-8th, 2016
Amsterdam, The Netherlands

Registries of domain-relevant semantic reference models help bootstrap interoperability in domains with fragmented data resources

The organisation of Bring Your Own Data (BYOD) workshops to make life science data linkable at the source

Since 2019 ISS partner of ELIXIR-IT

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Since 2014 «Rome BYOD»

At ISS National Centre for RDs with International Colleagues (...Friends)

A **BYOD** is a combination of hackathon and tutorial where data owners are trained to generate their own linkable data and create a simple showcase for linking their data to other data.

From the “RD Connect
BYOD to Link RD Registries”

To the “FAIRification of Data” in
the framework of the EJP RD

1st Edition 2014

10th Edition 2023

EJP RD in numbers

**+2600
people**

**35 participating
countries**

26 EU MS, 7 associated (AM, CH, GE, IL, NO, RS, TK), UK and CA

ALL 24 ERNs

**101 M€
Budget**

Union contribution: 55 M€ (70% reimbursement rate)

93 beneficiaries

10 hospitals

13 research institutes

31 research funding
bodies/ministries

28 universities/hospital universities

5 EU infrastructures

5 charities/foundations

EURORDIS

+ 48 linked third parties

**+100% associated
networks**

eatris

European Joint Programme on Rare Diseases – objectives & structure

- **Main objective:**

Create a research and innovation pipeline "from bench to bedside" ensuring rapid translation of research results into clinical applications and uptake in healthcare for the benefit of patients

- **Mode of action:**

Large programme that integrates existing infrastructures, trainings, funding programmes and tools, expands them and develops new essential ones to offer harmonized (and centralized) RD research ecosystem that is easy to use for scientists and produces benefits for patients in the most efficient way

Innovative coordinated access to data and services for transformative rare diseases research

Main Aim: FAIR Virtual Platform

- Federated
- Standardized
- GDPR-compliant
- Sustainable
- Quality assessed

1st Ed. of the virtual FAIR Data Game (2022)

Patient	1
Diagnose	Taaislijmziekte
Symptomen	Hoofd- en nekafwijking
Behandeling	(24S)-methylcalciol

Data Intelligence Just Accepted MS.
https://doi.org/10.1162/dint_a_00236

Building expertise on FAIR through evolving Bring Your Own Data (BYOD) workshops: describing the data, software, and management-focused approaches and their evolution

A Resource for Guiding Data Stewards to Make European Rare Disease Patient Registries FAIR

RESEARCH PAPER

 frontiers | Frontiers in **Molecular Biosciences**

TYPE Review
PUBLISHED 10 May 2023
DOI 10.3389/fmolb.2023.1169109

 Check for updates

Resources and tools for rare disease variant interpretation

OPEN ACCESS

From the “RD FAIR Data game” at ISS in Rome

Enhancing machine learning application for RD

To the First Edition of the NFDI4DS hackathon on “FAIR game for Research Software”
Koln, 6-8 November, 2023

June 28, 2023 (1.1) Other Open

The FAIR Game

Roos, Marco ; Carta, Claudio ; dos Santos Vieira, Bruna

September 27, 2021 (1.0) Presentation Open

BYOD Introduction & FAIR Game

Carta, Claudio ; Roos, Marco ; dos Santos Vieira, Bruna

A presentation about the FAIR game with game instructions

Uploaded on June 28, 2023

Published September 23, 2022 | Version 1.0

Video Tutorial for the FAIR Game

Cámara Ballesteros, Alberto¹ ; dos Santos Vieira, Bruna² ; Roos, Marco³ ; Carta, Claudio⁴ ; Bernabe, Cesar Henrique³ ; Zhang, Shuxin⁵ ; Benis, Nirupama⁵ ; van der Velde, Joeri⁶ ; Kalyaperumal, Rajaram³ ; Coelho de Oliveira Henriques, Ines²

January 12, 2022 (1.0) Poster Open

The 1st online Edition of the FAIR Data Game during the International Summer School on Rare Disease Registries & FAIRification of Data in Rome

Carta, Claudio ; dos Santos Vieira, Bruna ; Kalyaperumal, Rajaram

Rare Diseases Infrastructure

During 2019-21, this project will provide foundational infrastructure building blocks for the RD community, building on ELIXIR-supporting infrastructure and objectives:

- Data analysis
- Ensuring that data are findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable for humans and machines (FAIR)
- Training

Duration: 1 January 2019 to 31 December 2021

Platform/Community:

[Rare Diseases Community](#)

Nodes involved:

[ELIXIR Spain](#)

[ELIXIR Italy](#)

[ELIXIR Luxembourg](#)

[ELIXIR Netherlands](#)

[EMBL-EBI](#)

[ELIXIR France](#)

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ELIXIR Rare Disease Community services and international collaborations

To support such vision and facilitate data interoperability and analysis, the Community drives the assembly of service collections relevant for RD research, seeks interactions with other ELIXIR Human Data Communities to adapt and integrate resources and conducts Proof of Concept and pilot implementations of standards and methodologies.

OBJECTIVES

- Coordinate and align RD research activities related to data resources, tools and services within ELIXIR and with other European and International activities.
- Demonstrate the exploitation of FAIR data to reduce analytics complexity for data scientists
- Consolidate the recently created ELIXIR RD Service Collections (former “Bundles”)
- Disseminate and provide training on services and developments from the ELIXIR RD Community in collaboration with the ELIXIR Training Platform

Duration: 1 January 2022 to 31 December 2023

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START LEARNING

ELIXIR Rare Diseases Training Portal

The Rare Disease Community extends and generalises the system of access authorisation and high volume secure data transfer developed within the EGA project.

<https://rare-diseases.mf.uni-lj.si>

Hacking to FAIRify your training materials

9-10 March 2023, Rome Italy

Hackathon objectives:

- Learn how to FAIRify training materials using the FAIR Training Materials handbook as a self-learning tool
- Apply the content of the handbook to training materials
- Produce some sets of FAIRified training materials ready

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Thanks!